

rice soil, we mixed 5 ml or 10 ml of the fertilizer solution corresponding to 250 mg and 500 mg N/ pot, or 100 and 200 kg N/ ha. A clay pot with no applied N was the control. Treatments were replicated seven times, with one pot as a replication.

Three 7-d-old seedlings were transplanted in each pot. At 20 d after transplanting (DT), potted plants were covered with mylar film cages and infested with 20 newly hatched BPH nymphs per cage. After 18 d, or when insects reached adulthood, all but 3 pair (male and female, randomly selected) of BPH were removed. The six were left to develop a population in each cage. The insects removed from the cages were collected in vials, oven dried, and individually weighed. Because survival on IR60 was very low, no weights were

recorded. For the population growth test, BPH reared on IR26 plants in a separate cage were used to reinfest IR60 at 3 pair/ cage.

To determine the effect of BPH feeding rate at different N levels, one seedling was planted in a clay pot. At 30 DT, we recorded honeydew excretion (mm^2) by 5 adult females on filter paper treated with bromocresol green.

BPH weight (Fig. 1), feeding rate, and population growth (Fig. 2) increased with N application on IR26, Utri Rajapan, and Triveni. Population growth on IR26 and Utri Rajapan, without antibiotics, increased threefold with added N, and twofold on moderately resistant Triveni (Fig. 2). On IR26, Utri Rajapan, and Triveni, weight per female increased at both 250 and 500 mg N/ pot. Although IR60 was

2. BPH population development on selected varieties grown under different N fertilizer rates, IRRI.

highly resistant at the high N level and the BPH number remained low, the population doubled with applied N. \mathcal{L}

Insecticides to control thrips and caseworm in rice nurseries

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Thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnell) and caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* (Guen.) severely damage rice seedlings. We evaluated seed treatment and soil application of insecticides before and after sowing for their

control. CR1009 was planted in 4-m² plots. Thrips population was recorded on 10 randomly chosen seedlings/ plot at 20 and 30 d after sowing (DAS). At 30 DAS, percent caseworm damage was recorded for 10 seedlings/ plot based on total leaves and damaged leaves.

Broadcasting carbofuran 3 G at 0.5 kg ai/ ha before sowing and at 10 DAS controlled thrips most effectively. Broadcasting carbofuran at 10 DAS controlled caseworm most effectively (see table). \mathcal{L}

Insect pests of early season rice nurseries in the Imphal Valley

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In the Imphal Valley, cold weather prevents germination of rice seed in Feb

Varietal response to root aphid *Rhopalosiphum rufiabdominalis* (Sasaki) in winter rice nurseries, Imphal, India.

Variety	Aphid burns	
	No.	Area ^a (%)
Prasad (IR1561-2166)	8a	2 (7.99)
Punshi (IR661-1-140-3-2/Phouren)	8 ab	2 (7.87)
P-33 (TNI/Basmati 370)/(Ratna)	9ab	3 (9.13)
RCM-1 (Moirangphou/Jaya)	11 b	4 (11.06)
CH-1039	17 c	8 (16.52)
CD (P=0.05)	3	3

^a Values in the parentheses are arc sin percent transformation. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different.

Control of thrips and caseworm in rice nurseries, Tamil Nadu, India, 1984. ^a

Treatment	Thrips (no./seedling)		Caseworm (% damaged leaves) 30 DAS
	20 DAS	30 DAS	
Seed soaking ^b in chlorpyrifos, 0.2% for 3 h	0.5 c	0.9 bcd	12.0 b
Seed soaking ^b in chlorpyrifos, 0.1% for 3 h	0.4 bc	0.8 abcd	15.0 bc
Broadcasting carbofuran 3 G, 0.5 kg ai/ ha before sowing	0.1 a	0.4 ab	10.3 ab
Broadcasting phorate 10 G, 1.0 kg ai/ ha before sowing	0.2 ab	1.2 cd	12.3 b
Broadcasting carbofuran 3 G, 0.5 kg ai/ ha at 10 DAS	0.2 ab	0.3 a	4.8 a
Broadcasting phorate 10 G, 1.0 kg ai/ ha at 10 DAS	0.2 ab	0.6 abc	19.0 c
Untreated check	0.4 bc	1.3 d	13.5 bc
CD (0.05)	0.3	0.5	5.6

^a Values are means of 4 replications. DAS = days after sowing. Means in a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. ^b 12 ml (0.2%) and 6 ml (0.1%) of chlorpyrifos 20 EC used in 1.2 liters of water for soaking 1.0 kg seed.

and Mar and is a major constraint to the early rice crop. We tested a new nursery-raising method and thereby identified a new rice pest.

Five recommended high yielding rices (see table) were sown in early Feb 1983. Seeds were sown in 1-m² plots and were covered with 1 cm layer of soil and 1 cm of cow dung compost. Covering the plots with a polythene sheet for 2 wk significantly raised the temperature (14-40° C vs outside temperatures of 4-

21° C). When the sheet was removed, we found a serious infestation of rice root aphid *Rhopalosiphum rufiabdominalis* (Sasaki). The nursery remained yellowish with stunted growth until the end of Feb, and circular dead spots called *aphid burns* developed. When we pulled the seedlings, we found that Ch-1093 was most susceptible (see table). Sprinkling the nursery with phosphamidon at 0.05% concentration effectively controlled the aphids.

When similar nurseries were grown on a raised trench (30 × 30 × 150 cm), *Rhopalosiphum maidis* (Fitch) became a pest. Other insects associated with this nursery technique were phytophagous beetle *Luperodes* sp. and predator beetles, *Micraspis inops* var. *vincta* (Gorham) and *Paederus* sp. A fungivorous and phoretic mite, *Uroovovella* sp., was also found in the root zone. *ℒ*

Movement of BPMC in rice

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Because downward movement of BPMC (2-Sec-butyl phenyl N-methyl carbamate) in rice has been reported, we quantified movement of BPMC from rice leaves to stems.

We conducted 2 greenhouse pot trials in 0.3 × 0.4 × 0.2 m³ trays. The upper leaves of 30- and 60-d-old TN1 plants were treated with 0.2% and 0.4% solutions of BPMC 50EC with an atomizer at constant volume basis while the lower 15 cm of stems was protected with a thermocole. Leaves and stems of all plants were sampled at 0, 1, 3, and 4 d after treatment. Thirty-day-old plants also were sampled after 5 and 6 d. Treatments were in a complete randomized block design with three replications. Foliage and stem samples

BPMC residues in rice leaves and stems, Bhopal, India.

Sampling interval (d)	BPMC residue ^a (ppm)							
	30-d crop				60-d crop			
	0.2% concentration		0.4% concentration		0.2% concentration		0.4% concentration	
	Foliage	Stem	Foliage	Stem	Foliage	Stem	Foliage	Stem
0	8.4	BDL	21.6	BDL	9.5	BDL	41.5	BDL
1	7.3	0.8	17.6	2.1	8.0	0.9	34.8	3.6
2	3.8	0.9	13.8	2.3	4.7	1.0	24.4	4.2
3	2.4	0.5	7.2	1.3	2.7	0.6	19.2	4.2
4	1.1	0.3	3.1	0.7	1.4	0.4	4.4	1.6
5	0.4	BDL	0.9	0.6	—	—	—	—
6	0.3	BDL	0.4	0.2	—	—	—	—

^a Av of 3 replications. BDL = below detectable level (less than 0.10 ppm).

were separately analyzed by spectrophotometrics.

On treatment day, BPMC deposits on leaves of 30-d plants treated with 0.2 and 0.4% solutions were 8.4 and 22 ppm. Corresponding values for 60-d plants were 9 and 41 ppm (see table). Residue on the leaves degraded gradually, persisting for 4-6 d. About 9% of the insecticide had moved to the

stem 24 h after treatment. BPMC concentration in stems increased to about 11% 2 d after treatment and then gradually decreased. The decrease may be due to dilution as a result of plant growth or may be because dissipation exceeded the downward movement of BPMC. Neither plant age nor dosage significantly affected downward movement. *ℒ*

Insect pests of upland rice in Uttar Pradesh

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Upland rice in Uttar Pradesh is attacked by green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant), brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal), leafroller *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* (Guenee), butterfly *Melanitis leda ismene*

(Cramer), rice bug *Leptocorisa acuta* (Thunberg) (*-varicornis* Fab.), stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker), armyworm *Mythimna separata* (Walker), and aphid *Hysteroneura setariae* (Thomas). Of those, *N. virescens*, *L. varicornis*, *S. incertulas*, and *M. separata* are of major importance. In recent years, *M. separata* has become increasingly important, with severe infestations causing 60-80% yield losses. Losses to *L. acuta* are 15-20%, to *S. incertulas* 10-15%, and to *N. virescens* 5-10%. *ℒ*

Efficacy of three synthetic pyrethroids for caseworm control

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Caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* severely damages rice nurseries and young transplanted rice in thaladi (Nov-Dec) in Thanjavur district. Phosphamidon, monocrotophos, and endosulfan are recommended controls. We tested three synthetic pyrethroids for